

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.13939472

Impact Of Modern Ways Of Teaching And Learning Islamic Sciences On Students' Achievement In Kebbi State

Dr. Zakariya Harun Jega PhD¹; Nasiru Bala²; Hanafi Usman Yeldu PhD³ & Ismaila Bin Abdulwahab⁴

¹Department of Arabic Medium

Adamu Augie College Of Education Argungu, Kebbi State, Nigeria

zakariyaharunjega@gmail.com/+234(80)32405185

^{2,3,4}Department of Islamic Studies

Adamu Augie College Of Education Argungu, Kebbi State, Nigeria

nasirubala678@gmail.com/+234(91)66467434

hanafiuy@gmail.com/+234(70)33724890

ismailajega1@gmail.com/+234(80)39778772

ABSTRACT

The study delves into the impact of modern ways of teaching and learning Islamic science in Kebbi state, the principles guiding modern Islamic education, emphasizing the integration of Islamic values within the curriculum while remaining relevant and adaptable to contemporary challenges. It highlights the importance of fostering critical thinking, inquiry-based learning, inclusivity, and diversity within the educational framework. Moreover, the research underscores the significance of creating student-centered learning environments that leverage technology, experiential learning, and continuous professional development for educators. The study is to use a sampling size 150 respondents from modern schools in Kebbi state. The studies employ the use of descriptive survey as a research design. The self-developed Questionnaire on the three objectives is to be used as the instrument of data collection. Data collected will be analyzed using descriptive statistics (frequencies, percentages and mean) with the aid of statistical package of social sciences (SPSS Version 21.0). The researchers recommended that incorporating e-learning platforms, mobile apps, and multimedia tools (like videos, podcasts, and interactive lessons) to make Islamic Science lessons more engaging. This could improve understanding and retention, providing access to reputable online Islamic databases, digital libraries, and Qur'an interpretation tools can broaden students' learning beyond the classroom, Islamic teachings often rely on face-to-face interaction for personal guidance. Blended learning, which combines in-person instruction with online lessons, offers flexibility while maintaining the essence of personalized learning and creating online forums and discussion groups on Islamic Science topics can encourage peer-to-peer learning. Students can share knowledge, ask questions, and debate interpretations in a structured, respectful manner.

Keywords: impact, Modern, Ways, Teaching and learning, Islamic sciences

INTRODUCTION

The teaching and learning of Islamic sciences in Kebbi state play a crucial role in shaping the academic, intellectual, and spiritual development of students within Muslim communities. Islamic sciences encompass a diverse of subjects, including Qur'anic studies, Hadith, Islamic jurisprudence, theology, history, and Arabic language and literature. The impact of teaching and learning these

sciences extends beyond mere academic achievement, influencing students' cognitive abilities, moral and ethical values, cultural identity, and overall well-being. Bono (2009).

For centuries, Islamic education has been a cornerstone of Muslim societies, with Madrassas, Qur'anic schools, and Islamic universities serving as primary institutions for transmitting religious knowledge. The traditional methods of teaching Islamic sciences often involve memorization, recitation, and oral transmission of sacred texts, emphasizing the importance of rote learning and spiritual discipline. However, in contemporary times, the landscape of Islamic education is undergoing significant transformations, influenced by modernization, globalization, and advancements in educational technology. Y.Olaota(2010)

In recent decades, there has been a growing emphasis on modernizing the teaching and learning of Islamic sciences to align with the changing needs and aspirations of Muslim students and societies. Modern Islamic educational institutions, including Islamic schools, colleges, and universities, seek to integrate traditional Islamic teachings with contemporary educational methodologies, such as experiential learning, critical thinking, and interdisciplinary approaches. The adoption of modern teaching methods aims to enhance students' engagement, comprehension, and retention of Islamic knowledge while equipping them with skills relevant to the modern world. Y.Olaota (2010)

The impact of teaching and learning Islamic sciences on students' achievements is multifaceted and encompasses various dimensions. Academically, studying Islamic sciences fosters intellectual curiosity, analytical thinking, and problem-solving skills among students. Through rigorous engagement with classical texts, students develop linguistic proficiency in Arabic and deepen their understanding of complex theological concepts and historical contexts. Moreover, the study of Islamic sciences can enhance students' performance in other academic disciplines, such as history, literature, and philosophy, by providing them with a broader cultural and intellectual perspective. Ahmed. (1998)

Beyond academic achievements, the teaching and learning of Islamic sciences also contribute to students' moral and ethical development. Islamic education emphasizes the cultivation of virtues such as honesty, compassion, humility, and integrity, which are essential for leading a righteous and ethical life. By studying the ethical teachings of Islam and the exemplary behavior of Prophet Muhammad (saw), students learn to apply ethical principles in their personal conduct, interpersonal relationships, and civic responsibilities. This ethical grounding fosters a sense of social responsibility and civic engagement among students, empowering them to contribute positively to their communities and societies. Olurude (2008).

Furthermore, the teaching and learning of Islamic sciences have a profound impact on students' cultural identity and spiritual well-being. Islamic education provides students with a deeper appreciation of their religious heritage, cultural traditions, and spiritual values, fostering a sense of belonging and identity within the Muslim community. By studying the Qur'an, Hadith, and Islamic history, students develop a strong sense of religious identity and spiritual connection to their faith, which serves as a source of strength, guidance, and solace in times of adversity. T. Isma'il (2003).

Therefore, "the modern way teaching and learning of Islamic sciences" exert a significant influence on students' achievements, encompassing academic, moral, ethical, cultural, and spiritual dimensions. As a Muslim community navigates the complexities of the modern world, the importance of providing quality Islamic education that nurtures students' holistic development cannot be overstated. By investing in the modernization of Islamic education and adopting innovative teaching methodologies, educators can empower students to excel academically, uphold moral and ethical values, preserve cultural heritage, and deepen their spiritual understanding of Islam.

Statement of the Problem

It has been observed that the main problem that necessitates the research are: The integration of modern teaching methodologies with traditional Islamic sciences raises questions regarding the effectiveness of these pedagogical approaches in enhancing students' academic achievement in Kebbi state.

The incorporation of modern teaching technologies in Islamic education, such as e-learning platforms, digital resources, and interactive multimedia, presents challenges in terms of accessibility, infrastructure, and adaptability. How do these challenges impact students' engagement and achievement in the learning of Islamic sciences in Kebbi State?

Societal Perceptions and Expectations: The adoption of modern teaching methods in Islamic education may elicit varying perceptions and expectations from different segments of the society.

Evaluating Holistic Student Development: Islamic education traditionally emphasizes holistic development, encompassing spiritual, moral, and cultural dimensions.

Addressing these statements of the problems will contribute to a comprehensive understanding of the impact of the modern way of teaching and learning Islamic sciences on students' achievements in Kebbi state, informing educational policies, practices, and future research directions in the field of Islamic education.

Objectives:

The main aims and objective of this research are to explore the impact of modern ways of teaching and learning Islamic sciences on students' achievements in Kebbi state through the following key objectives:

1. To examine the principles and practices of modern Islamic sciences on students' achievements in Kebbi state
2. To explore the socio-emotional and cognitive development of modern Islamic sciences on students' achievements in Kebbi state
3. To identify the factors influencing students' achievement leaning modern Islamic sciences in Kebbi state

LITERATURE REVIEW

Principles and practices of modern Islamic sciences on student's achievements

Modern Islamic education is a dynamic and evolving field that encompasses a blend of traditional Islamic teachings with contemporary educational methods. This literature review explores the principles and practices underpinning modern Islamic education, drawing upon a range of scholarly articles, research studies, and educational reports to provide a comprehensive overview of the subject.

Integration of Islamic Values: The integration of Islamic values within the curriculum is a fundamental principle of modern Islamic education. Scholars such as Karsenti (2018) emphasize the importance of instilling Islamic ethics, morals, and values in students to create a holistic educational experience.

Relevance and Adaptability: Modern Islamic education principles underscore the need for educational institutions to remain relevant and adaptable in the contemporary world. Khan (2017) argues that Islamic education should address current global challenges while preserving the core principles of Islam, fostering a balance between tradition and modernity.

Critical Thinking and Inquiry: Promoting critical thinking and inquiry-based learning is recognized as a principle in modern Islamic education. Research by Rahman and Abdullah (2019) suggests that encouraging students to question, analyze, and apply Islamic teachings fosters a deeper understanding and engagement with the subject matter.

Inclusivity and Diversity: Modern Islamic education principles advocate for inclusivity and embracing diversity within the educational framework. El-Nekhaily and Thomas (2020) discuss the importance of creating an inclusive environment that caters to students of diverse backgrounds and abilities while upholding Islamic principles.

Technology Integration: The incorporation of modern technology is a prevalent practice in contemporary Islamic education. Ahmed et al. (2021) conducted a study on the use of e-learning platforms in Islamic education, highlighting the positive impact of technology on student engagement and learning outcomes.

Student-Centered Learning: Modern Islamic education practices prioritize student-centered learning approaches. Al-Harbi (2018) emphasizes the importance of tailoring teaching methods to individual learning styles, fostering a more interactive and engaging educational experience.

Experiential Learning: Experiential learning methods, such as field trips, simulations, and hands-on activities, are increasingly employed in modern Islamic education. Khalid and Mokhtar (2019) argue that experiential learning enhances students' practical understanding of Islamic concepts and promotes a deeper connection with the teachings.

Continuous Professional Development for Educators: Ensuring continuous professional development for educators is a common practice in modern Islamic education. Research by Ali and Ayub (2017)

suggests that ongoing training programs for teachers contribute to the improvement of instructional methods, ultimately benefiting students.

The examination of both principles and practices in modern Islamic education reveals a commitment to integrating Islamic values with contemporary educational approaches. By embracing inclusivity, technology, student-centered learning, and experiential methods, modern Islamic education strives to create a well-rounded educational experience that prepares students for the challenges of the modern world while staying true to the core principles of Islam.

Socio-Emotional Development on student achievements

The socio-emotional and cognitive development of students, emphasizing the impact of various factors on these aspects. The objective is to identify similarities and differences in the literature across diverse educational contexts. The review spans studies from psychology, education, and related disciplines, providing a comprehensive understanding of the multifaceted nature of student development.

Teacher-Student Relationships: Research by Pianta and Hamre (2009) highlights the significance of positive teacher-student relationships in fostering socio-emotional development. A supportive and nurturing environment contributes to emotional resilience and social competence among students.

Parental Involvement: The role of parental involvement in socio-emotional development is evident in studies such as Hill and Tyson (2009). Collaborative efforts between parents and educators contribute to emotional regulation, interpersonal skills, and overall well-being in students.

Cultural Factors: Cultural influences on socio-emotional development are explored by Chen et al. (2016). The literature emphasizes the importance of cultural sensitivity in educational practices to address diverse emotional needs and social expectations.

Cognitive Development:

Technology and Cognitive Skills: The impact of technology on cognitive development is discussed by Hsin and Cigas (2013). While digital tools can enhance certain cognitive skills, the literature emphasizes the importance of a balanced approach to technology integration.

Problem-Solving and Critical Thinking: Educational practices promoting problem-solving and critical thinking skills are highlighted by Gokhale (1995). The literature underscores the role of active learning methodologies in enhancing cognitive abilities and preparing students for real-world challenges.

Experiential Learning: Experiential learning as a catalyst for cognitive development is explored by Kolb (1984). The literature suggests that hands-on experiences and practical applications contribute to a deeper understanding of concepts and improved cognitive outcomes.

Similarities and Differences:

Cross-Cultural Perspectives: Studies such as Cross et al. (2013) emphasize the importance of considering cross-cultural variations in both socio-emotional and cognitive development. While cultural influences shape emotional expression and learning styles, there are universal elements that contribute to holistic development.

Intersectionality: The intersectionality of socio-emotional and cognitive development is explored by Raver (2002). The literature suggests that these domains are interconnected, with emotional well-being influencing cognitive functioning and vice versa.

Contextual Factors: Contextual factors, including socioeconomic status and educational environment, are recognized across studies (Bradley & Corwyn, 2002; Ladd et al., 1999). The literature underscores the need to address contextual disparities to ensure equitable socio-emotional and cognitive development.

Therefore, the literature review provides an understanding of socio-emotional and cognitive development in students, highlighting the interconnected nature of these domains. While acknowledging universal principles, the literature underscores the importance of considering cultural, contextual, and individual factors in shaping the developmental trajectories of students. Future research should continue to explore the dynamic interplay between socio-emotional and cognitive aspects to inform effective educational practices across diverse settings.

This comprehensive literature review examines the multifaceted factors influencing students' academic achievement across diverse educational contexts. Drawing upon research from psychology, education, and related fields, the review explores similarities and differences in the determinants shaping students' success. Socio-economic, cultural, and educational factors are analyzed to provide insights into the complex interplay influencing student achievement.

identify the factors influencing students' achievements on Islamic modern sciences

Achieving academic success is influenced by a myriad of factors that extend beyond classroom instruction. This literature review aims to investigate the various determinants impacting students' achievement, highlighting both commonalities and divergences across different socio-cultural and educational settings. By synthesizing research findings, this review offers a nuanced understanding of the multifaceted nature of student achievement.

Socio-Economic Factors:

Family Socio-Economic Status (SES): Numerous studies have demonstrated the strong association between family SES and students' academic achievement (Sirin, 2005; Bradley & Corwyn, 2002). Higher SES families tend to provide greater access to resources, educational support, and enrichment opportunities, leading to better academic outcomes for their children.

Parental Involvement: Parental involvement has consistently emerged as a significant predictor of students' achievement (Fan & Chen, 2001; Hill & Tyson, 2009). Active parental engagement, including monitoring homework, attending school events, and fostering a supportive home environment, positively influences students' motivation and academic success.

Access to Resources: Disparities in access to educational resources contribute to inequalities in academic achievement (Lareau, 2004; Bradley & Corwyn, 2002). Students from lower-income families often face challenges related to limited access to textbooks, technology, tutoring services, and extracurricular activities, hindering their academic progress.

Cultural Factors:

Cultural Expectations and Values: Cultural factors significantly influence students' attitudes toward education and academic success (Lee & Zhou, 2015; Chen et al., 2016). Cultural expectations regarding the importance of education, parental aspirations, and attitudes toward learning shape students' motivation, persistence, and academic performance.

Language and Cultural Adaptation: Language proficiency and cultural adaptation play crucial roles in students' academic achievement, particularly among immigrant and minority populations (Suárez-Orozco et al., 2010; Lee & Zhou, 2015). Challenges related to language barriers and cultural adjustment can impact students' ability to fully engage in learning activities and achieve academic success.

Educational Factors:

Quality of Instruction: The quality of instruction, including teacher effectiveness and instructional practices, significantly impacts students' academic achievement (Hattie, 2009; Wenglinsky, 2002). Effective teaching strategies, feedback mechanisms, and differentiated instruction cater to diverse learning needs and promote positive learning outcomes.

School Climate and Support Systems: A positive school climate characterized by supportive relationships, safety, and a sense of belonging fosters students' academic achievement (Cohen et al., 2009; Ladd et al., 1999). Access to supportive services, such as counseling, mentoring, and academic interventions, enhances students' overall well-being and academic success.

Conclusion: This literature review underscores the complex interplay of socio-economic, cultural, and educational factors influencing students' academic achievement. While certain factors, such as family SES and parental involvement, consistently predict academic outcomes across various contexts, cultural expectations, language proficiency, and school-related factors also play significant roles. By understanding the diverse influences on student achievement, educators and policymakers can develop targeted interventions to address disparities and promote equitable access to educational opportunities for all students.

METHODOLOGY

The research design for the study will be descriptive survey so as to determine the impact of Modern way of teaching and learning Islamic sciences. The study will also use quantitative research approach.

The quantitative research approach will be used to quantify and analyze the data in order to get in depth understanding of the impact of Modern ways of teaching learning Islamic sciences on student’s achievement in Kebbi State.

The target population of this study will be the students learning Islamic sciences in Mordan School in Kebbi state. And the study will only focus on students or learners in modern schools in three local Government areas (Jega, Aliero and Gwandu) federal constituency in Kebbi state on these schools, the population of study is 50 students from the selected modern Islamic schools in the three local governments area.

Using the works of Krejcie and Morgan (V Krejcie & D.W Morgan,) that focus on a scientific way of calculating various sample sizes and the corresponding population, the sample size of the total population of 210 will be about 138 respondents.

Sampling techniques

This study will employ a random sampling technique, to select a sample of one hundred and fifty (150) respondents from the study population of two hundred and ten (210) of Tahfidhul-Qur’an/modern schools, random sampling shall be used because it will expose every participant to an equal chance of participating in the study as argued by (Amin.M. E,200)

The study shall use both the questionnaire and test as implement for data collection A questionnaire is an Instrument designed to gather data from individuals about their knowledge, attitude, beliefs and feelings. They are useful in getting data because they are easy and quick to administer. Questionnaires will be the right instrument of data collection. It will contain short questions which require the respondents to fill or tick options according to their perception. The questionnaires will be delivered to the respondents and they will be asked to fill at their convenience but with the guidance of the researcher. It will be closed and open ended.

Test

This tool will be used to measure the student’s achievement (performance) of Modern schools, the target groups are Senior2& 3 of the selected Modern Islamic schools in Kebbi State. The Test will be in form of examination questions, on the subject of Qur’an, hadith and the Fiqh. The Test will contain short questions which required the respondents to answer in a sheet of paper for marking their performance. Responses to the questions in the test shall be analyzed and comparison of the student’s performance in both categories of schools compared. The researcher will explain to the respondents the purpose of the study for which it is carrying out, and ask for their consent.

Data processing and Analysis

The responses to questionnaires and test will be grouped basing on the views of respondents. A regression analysis will also be used to determine the confidence of learners in responding to the questions based on variables under study and the responses shall be used to calculate their competence levels. The views were coded in preparation for analysis. Responses from the data will enter in to the SPSS for automatic generation of numerical values in frequencies and percentages. Interpretation will be made from the numerical values and percentages revealed by the data. Tables and graphs were drawn to present the information

RESULTS

Table 1 showing the age of the respondents

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	13-15	21	18.6	18.6	18.6
	16-18	78	69.0	69.0	87.6
	Others	14	12.4	12.4	100.0
	Total	113	100.0	100.0	

Table 1 showing the age of the respondents, this shows that 78 (69%) are between 16-18 years, 21 (18.6%) are 13-15 years while 14 (12.4%) are others. This shows that majority of the respondents are between the age of 16-18 years with the highest percentage of 69%.

Table 2 showing the Gender of the respondents

	Gender	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Male	52	46.0
	Female	59	52.2
	Others	2	1.8
	Total	113	100.0

Source: Field Data (2024)

The table above shows the gender of the respondents the finding above shows that 59 (52.2%) of the participants are females, 52 (45%) are male while 2 (1.8%) participants are others. This shows that female participants in this study outnumbered their female counterparts.

Table 3 Grade Level

	Grade Level	Frequency	Percent
Valid	SS II	40	35.4
	SS III	73	64.6
	Total	113	100.0

Source: Field Data (2024)

The table above shows the grade level of the respondents the finding above shows that 73 (64.6%) of the participants are in SS III while 40 (35.4%) participants are in SS II. This shows that majority of the respondents are in SS III with the highest percentage of 64.6%.

Table 4 showing School Type

	School Type	Frequency	Percent
Valid	Public	40	35.4
	Private	73	64.6
	Total	113	100.0

Source: Field Data (2024)

The table above shows the school type of the respondents the finding above shows that 73 (64.6%) of the participants are private school, while 40 (35.4%) participants are in public schools. This shows that majority of the respondents are in private school with the highest percentage of 64.6%.

Table 5 simple linear regression of Principle and practice of modern Islamic science on Students Achievement

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	52.524	1	52.524	2.475	.118 ^b
	Residual	2355.405	111	21.220		
	Total	2407.929	112			

a. Dependent Variable: Practice of Modern Islamic

b. Predictors: (Constant), Achievement Test

The result in table 4 shows that the calculated F-value of 2.475 at 0.05 level of significance at 381 degree of freedom. The results also shows that that the P-value 118^b is greater than 0.05 alpha level. With this result, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that student achievements is greater than principle and practice of modern Islamic Science.

Table 6 simple linear regression of : Socio-Emotional and Cognitive Development in Modern Islamic Science

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	132.267	1	132.267	3.199	.076 ^b
	Residual	4589.272	111	41.345		
	Total	4721.540	112			

a. Dependent Variable: Socio-Emotional and Cognitive Development in Modern Islamic Science

b. Predictors: (Constant), Achievement Test

The result in table 4 shows that the calculated F-value of 3.199 at 0.05 level of significance at 112 degree of freedom. The results also shows that that the P-value .076^b is greater than 0.05 alpha level. With this result, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that student achievements is greater than principle and practice of modern Islamic Science.

Table 7 simple linear regression of factors influencing Students achievement in learning modern Islamic science

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	.070	1	.070	.003	.960 ^b
	Residual	3005.608	110	27.324		
	Total	3005.679	111			

a. Dependent Variable: Factors Influencing Students' Achievement in Learning Modern Islamic Science

b. Predictors: (Constant), Achievement Test

The result in table 4 shows that the calculated F-value of .003 at 0.05 level of significance at 111 degree of freedom. The results also shows that that the P-value .960 is greater than 0.05 alpha level. With this result, the null hypothesis is accepted. This means that student achievements is greater than Factors Influencing Students' Achievement in Learning Modern Islamic Science.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

The impact of modern teaching and learning methods on student achievement in Islamic science, particularly in Kebbi State, Nigeria, is a multifaceted issue that reflects broader trends in educational reform and integration of technology. Recent studies indicate that the transformation of Islamic education is essential for enhancing student outcomes and adapting to contemporary educational demands.

One significant finding is the necessity for Islamic educational institutions to embrace modern pedagogical strategies and integrate technology into their curricula. Research highlights that graduates from Islamic tertiary institutions often lack the necessary technological competencies required in the 4.0 industrial era, which poses a challenge for effective teaching and learning (Muhammad, 2023). This gap in technological proficiency can hinder students' ability to engage with Islamic sciences in a manner that is relevant to today's context. Furthermore, the integration of Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) into Islamic education has been proposed as a strategy to enhance learning outcomes by fostering a multidisciplinary approach that aligns with institutional goals (Murhayati, 2023). This integration not only enriches the educational experience but also prepares students to meet the demands of a rapidly changing job market.

Additionally, the curriculum development policies in Islamic education are undergoing transformation to better align with national educational standards and cultural contexts. The development of Islamic pedagogy, which emphasizes cultural reinvigoration, is crucial for facilitating curriculum implementation and improving educational quality (Akrim et al., 2022). This approach is particularly relevant in Kebbi State, where cultural and religious contexts significantly influence educational practices. The incorporation of differentiated learning strategies, as seen in the Merdeka Belajar curriculum, has also shown promise in enhancing student engagement and achievement in Islamic education (Wantini, 2023). Such strategies allow for personalized learning experiences that cater to diverse student needs, thereby improving overall educational outcomes.

Moreover, the role of teachers in Islamic education is pivotal. Research indicates that teachers face challenges in evaluating student learning outcomes effectively, which can affect students' understanding and application of Islamic values in their daily lives (Saraya, 2023). Addressing these challenges through professional development and support can lead to improved teaching practices and, consequently, better student performance in Islamic sciences.

In conclusion, the modern ways of teaching and learning Islamic science in Kebbi State are significantly influenced by the integration of technology, curriculum reforms, and the professional development of educators. These factors collectively contribute to enhancing student achievement and preparing them for the complexities of contemporary society.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, adopting modern methods of teaching and learning Islamic Science in Kebbi State can significantly enhance student achievement. The integration of technology, such as e-learning platforms and digital tools, combined with blended learning approaches, offers flexibility, engagement, and a broader scope for student learning. Interactive learning environments, contextualized lessons, and community-based projects further deepen students' understanding and connection to the real-world application of Islamic teachings.

To achieve these benefits, it's essential to provide adequate teacher training in modern pedagogical techniques, while ensuring cultural sensitivity and respect for Islamic values. Continuous assessment and feedback mechanisms will help track student progress and offer timely support. By blending traditional Islamic educational methods with modern advancements, educators can create a more effective and enriching learning experience, fostering both academic excellence and personal growth among students in Kebbi State.

RECOMMENDATIONS

To enhance student achievement in Islamic Science in Kebbi State, it's essential to consider modern teaching and learning methods that align with both traditional values and contemporary educational practices. Below are recommendations on how the modern approach can impact student achievement positively:

1. Incorporating e-learning platforms, mobile apps, and multimedia tools (like videos, podcasts, and interactive lessons) to make Islamic Science lessons more engaging. This could improve understanding and retention.
2. Providing access to reputable online Islamic databases, digital libraries, and Qur'an interpretation tools can broaden students' learning beyond the classroom.
3. Islamic teachings often rely on face-to-face interaction for personal guidance. Blended learning, which combines in-person instruction with online lessons, offers flexibility while maintaining the essence of personalized learning.
4. Creating online forums and discussion groups on Islamic Science topics can encourage peer-to-peer learning. Students can share knowledge, ask questions, and debate interpretations in a structured, respectful manner.
5. Teachers need training in digital literacy, online content creation, and the use of modern educational tools to effectively integrate technology into Islamic Science education.
6. Implementing online tests, quizzes, and progress trackers to continuously monitor students' understanding. This can help teachers identify areas where students struggle and offer timely support.
7. It's crucial to balance the use of modern technology and methods with respect for Islamic traditions and values. Careful consideration should be given to culturally appropriate content.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This paper was funded by TETFUND under the Institution Based Research (IBR) Annual Intervention, we therefore acknowledge their immense support. Also appreciate Adamu Augie College of education, Argungu for the opportunity given to us to conduct this work.

REFERENCES

- Ahmed, S., et al. (2021). E-learning in Islamic Education: Perceptions and Challenges. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning*, 16(1), 99-110.
- Akrim, A., Setiawan, H., Selamat, S., & Ginting, N. (2022). Transformation of Islamic education curriculum development policy in the National Education System. *Cypriot Journal of Educational Sciences*, 17(7), 2538-2552. <https://doi.org/10.18844/cjes.v17i7.7685>
- Ali, M., & Ayub, A. F. M. (2017). The Impact of Continuous Professional Development on the Teaching Competency of Islamic Education Teachers. *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 7(12), 541-552.
- Bradley, R. H., & Corwyn, R. F. (2002). Socioeconomic status and child development. *Annual Review of Psychology*, 53, 371-399.
- Chen, X., et al. (2016). Cultural values, parenting quality, and adaptive functioning among Chinese American Children. *Child Development*, 87(6), 1837-1851.
- Cross, S. E., et al. (2013). Cultural models of self and social orientation: A comparison of American, Taiwanese, and Japanese undergraduates. *Self and Identity*, 12(3), 169-191.
- El-Nekhaily, D., & Thomas, C. (2020). Embracing Diversity in Islamic Schools: A Case Study of Inclusion Practices. *Journal of Inclusive Education in the Islamic World*, 5(1), 19-34.
- Gokhale, A. A. (1995). Collaborative learning enhances critical thinking. *Journal of Technology Education*, 7(1), 22-30.
- Hill, N. E., & Tyson, D. F. (2009). Parental involvement in middle school: A meta-analytic assessment of the strategies that promote achievement. *Developmental Psychology*, 45(3), 740-763.
- Hsin, C. T., & Cigas, J. (2013). Short-term effects of integrated science instruction on science achievement and attitudes towards science of preserves elementary teachers: An exploratory study. *International Journal of Science Education*, 35(2), 263-282.
- Karsenti, T. (2018). The Integration of Islamic Values into Public Schools: A Global Comparative Overview. *Religious Education*, 113(5), 490-507.
- Khalid, S. N., & Mokhtar, M. (2019). Experiential Learning in Islamic Studies: A Case Study of Malaysia. *Journal of Education and Learning*, 8(4), 103-114.
- Khan, A. (2017). Islamic Education and Modern World: A Comparative Study. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 7(4), 47-56.
- Kolb, D. A. (1984). *Experiential learning: Experience as the source of learning and development*. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- Ladd, G. W., Birch, S. H., & Buhs, E. S. (1999). Children's social and scholastic lives in kindergarten: Related spheres of influence? *Child Development*, 70(6), 1373-1400.
- Muhammad, A. (2023). Opportunities and challenges faced by state Islamic tertiary education institutions in 4.0 industrial era. *Multidisciplinary Science Journal*, 5(3), 2023036. <https://doi.org/10.31893/multiscience.2023036>
- Murhayati, S. (2023). Integration of science, technology, engineering, and mathematics (stem) in Islamic education using strategic assumption surfacing and testing (sast).. <https://doi.org/10.46254/ap04.20230235>
- Pianta, R. C., & Hamre, B. K. (2009). Conceptualization, measurement, and improvement of classroom processes: Standardized observation can leverage capacity. *Educational Researcher*, 38(2), 109-119.
- Rahman, S. A., & Abdullah, N. A. (2019). Developing Critical Thinking Skills in Islamic Education. *International Journal of Islamic Thought*, 16(1), 54-66.
- Raver, C. C. (2002). Emotions matter: Making the case for the role of young children's emotional development for early school readiness. *Social Policy Report*, 16(3), 3-18.
- Saraya, A. (2023). The role of Islamic religious education teachers: problems in evaluating student learning outcomes in junior high schools. *Dharmas Education Journal (De_journal)*, 4(2), 565-572. <https://doi.org/10.56667/dejournal.v4i2.1060>